

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

SOLUTION OF ONE MIXED PROBLEM FOR A ROD IN A MEDIUM WITH RESISTANCE

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Abstract

The presented article provides an analytical solution to a mixed problem for the equation of rod vibrations. This equation is atypical, of the fourth order. The interesting side is that the corresponding spectral problem is not self-adjoint, and the eigenvalues have a second multiplicity. As you know, in this case, the usual Fourier method (based on orthogonality) is not applicable. The regularity of the spectral problem in the sense of Rasulov makes it possible to successfully apply the residue method and construct a solution in the form of a series.

Keywords: mixed problem, Rasulov residue method, Green's function, pole.

As is known, the equation of rod oscillations plays a fundamental role in the theory of oscillations and the dynamics of elastic systems, and is the "ABC" of wave mechanics of solids. This equation is the basic model of elastic systems - it is used to learn to understand wave processes, natural frequencies, and oscillation modes. It is used in structural mechanics and mechanical engineering, acoustics, aerospace engineering, seismology, nanotechnology, etc.

This article considers a boundary value problem on small transverse vibrations of a rectangular homogeneous elastic rod in a medium with resistance proportional to velocity, under the action of a continuously distributed external transverse force [1]. These vibrations, i.e., the transverse displacements of the rod's points from their equilibrium position, are described by the equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + a^2 \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial x^4} + 2v^2 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = f(x, t),$$

at $0 < x < 1, 0 < t < T$, where $a^2 = \frac{EJ}{\rho s}$, $2v^2 = \frac{k}{\rho}$,

E – modulus of elasticity of the rod,

s – cross-sectional area of the rod,

ρ – rod mass density,

k – coefficient of friction,

J – the symmetric moment of inertia of the cross-section with respect to its centroidal axis perpendicular to the plane of vibration.

So, a mixed problem of finding the solution of the equation is considered

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + a^2 \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial x^4} + 2v^2 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = f(x, t), 0 < x < 1, 0 < t < T, (1)$$

under boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u(0, t) &= 0, \\ u'_x(0, t) - u'_x(1, t) &= 0, \\ u''(0, t) &= 0, \\ u'''_x(0, t) - u'''_x(1, t) &= 0, \end{aligned} (2)$$

and initial conditions

$$\left. \frac{\partial^k u}{\partial t^k} \right|_{t=0} = \varphi_k(x), k = 0, 1. (3)$$

To solve problem (1)–(2)–(3), we apply the residue method developed by M. Rasulov [3], since the most commonly used approach—the Fourier method of separation of variables—encounters serious difficulties due to the fact that the corresponding spectral problem is non-self-adjoint. In such a case, the eigenfunctions may fail to form an orthogonal and complete system, and the usual Fourier expansion is not applicable [2]. Moreover, because of the multiplicity of eigenvalues, the Fourier–Birkhoff method (the method of biorthogonal functions) cannot be used either.

The solution to problem (1)–(2)–(3) is sought in the form of a series [3],

$$u(x, t) = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_v \int_{C_v} \lambda^3 d\lambda \int_0^1 G(x, \xi, \lambda) z(t, \xi, \lambda) d\xi, (4)$$

where $G(x, \xi, \lambda)$ is the Green's function of the spectral problem

$$\frac{d^4 y}{dx^4} - \lambda^4 y = h(x), (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} y(0) = 0, y'(0) - y'(1) = 0, \\ y''(0) = 0, y'''(0) - y'''(1) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

C_ν - a simple closed contour enclosing the λ_ν of the Green's function and the sum over ν is taken over all poles, $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

It is known that, in the case of regularity of the spectral problem, any continuously differentiable function $h(x) \in C^1(0,1)$ can be represented as an expansion in a series of complete integral residues [3],

$$h(x) = -\sum_{\nu} \operatorname{Res}_{\nu} \lambda^3 \int_0^1 G(x, \xi, \lambda) h(\xi) d\xi = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{\nu} \int_{C_\nu} \lambda^3 d\lambda \int_0^1 G(x, \xi, \lambda) h(\xi) d\xi, \quad (7)$$

$$x \in (0,1).$$

Using formula (4) for the solution and the expansion (7) for the function $Z(t, x, \lambda)$ we arrive at the following Cauchy problem:

$$\frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} + 2v^2 \frac{dz}{dt} + \lambda^4 a^2 z = f(x, t), \quad (8)$$

$$z(0) = \varphi_0(x),$$

$$z'_t(0) = \varphi_1(x). \quad (9)$$

By applying the method of variation of constants, the general solution of equation (8) is constructed. Then, taking into account the initial data (9), the solution of problem (8)–(9) is obtained:

$$Z(t, x, \lambda) = \frac{-1}{2\sqrt{v^4 - \lambda^4 a^2}} \left[(\varphi_0(x) m_2 - \varphi_1(x)) e^{m_1 t} + (\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_0(x) m_1) e^{m_2 t} + \int_0^t f(x, \tau) (e^{m_2(t-\tau)} - e^{m_1(t-\tau)}) d\tau \right], \quad (10)$$

where

$$m_1 = -v^2 + \sqrt{v^4 - \lambda^4 a^2}, \quad m_2 = -v^2 - \sqrt{v^4 - \lambda^4 a^2}.$$

After some simplifications, from (10) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} Z(t, x, \lambda) = & \varphi_0(x) e^{-v^2 t} \cos \sqrt{\lambda^4 a^2 - v^4} t + \\ & + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda^4 a^2 - v^4}} (\varphi_1(x) + v^2 \varphi_0(x)) e^{-v^2 t} \sin \sqrt{\lambda^4 a^2 - v^4} t + \\ & + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda^4 a^2 - v^4}} \int_0^t f(x, \tau) e^{-v^2(t-\tau)} \sin \sqrt{\lambda^4 a^2 - v^4} (t-\tau) d\tau \end{aligned}$$

The Green's function of problem (5)–(6) is a meromorphic function, which can be represented as

$$G(x, \xi, \lambda) = \frac{\Delta(x, \xi, \lambda)}{\Delta(\lambda)},$$

where the functions $\Delta(x, \xi, \lambda)$ and $\Delta(\lambda)$ are constructed using known formulas based on the fundamental solutions of the equation $y^{IV} - \lambda^4 y = 0$ and the boundary conditions (6).

The poles of the Green's function are the zeros of the so-called characteristic determinant $\Delta(\lambda)$. In our case, it is defined by the formula

$$\Delta(\lambda) = 4i\lambda^6 e^{-\lambda(1+i)} (1 - e^\lambda)^2 (e^{i\lambda} - 1)^2 \quad (11)$$

and it has two sequences of multiple zeros

$$\lambda_{\nu_1} = 2\pi\nu, \quad \lambda_{\nu_2} = 2\pi\nu i, \quad (\nu = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots) \quad (12)$$

which are poles of second order for the Green's function.

The numerator $\Delta(x, \xi, \lambda)$ of the Green's function is given by the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(x, \xi, \lambda) = & g(x, \xi, \lambda) \Delta(\lambda) - i\lambda^3 \frac{e^{\lambda x}}{2} \left[e^{-\lambda(1+i)} (1 - e^\lambda) (1 - e^{i\lambda})^2 (e^{\lambda\xi} - e^{-\lambda\xi}) \right] \\ & + i\lambda^3 e^{-\lambda x} \left[e^{i\lambda} (1 - e^\lambda) (1 - e^{i\lambda})^2 (e^{\lambda\xi} - e^{-\lambda\xi}) \right] - \\ & - (e^{\lambda x} - e^{-\lambda x}) \frac{i\lambda^3}{2} \left[e^{-i\lambda} (1 - e^{i\lambda})^2 (e^{\lambda\xi} + e^{-\lambda\xi} + e^{\lambda(1-\xi)} + e^{-\lambda(1-\xi)}) \right] \\ & + \frac{\lambda^3}{2} e^{i\lambda x} \left[e^{-\lambda(1+i)} (1 - e^{i\lambda}) (1 - e^\lambda)^2 (e^{i\lambda\xi} - e^{-i\lambda\xi}) \right] - \\ & - \frac{\lambda^3}{2} e^{-i\lambda x} \left[e^{-\lambda} (1 - e^{i\lambda}) (1 - e^\lambda)^2 (e^{i\lambda\xi} - e^{-i\lambda\xi}) \right] + \\ & + \frac{\lambda^3}{2} (e^{i\lambda x} - e^{-i\lambda x}) \left[e^{-\lambda} (1 - e^\lambda)^2 (e^{i\lambda\xi} + e^{-i\lambda\xi} + e^{i\lambda(1-\xi)} + e^{-i\lambda(1-\xi)}) \right], \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } g(x, \xi, \lambda) = \pm \frac{1}{8\lambda^3} \left[e^{\lambda(x-\xi)} - e^{-\lambda(x-\xi)} + i(e^{i\lambda(x-\xi)} - e^{-i\lambda(x-\xi)}) \right].$$

It is not difficult to verify the regularity of the spectral problem in the sense of M. Rasulov and to check the boundedness of the solution of the Cauchy problem on the spectrum (12). These conditions ensure the existence and uniqueness of the solution to problem (1)–(3) [3]. By calculating the residues with respect to the multiple poles λ_{ν_1} and λ_{ν_2} , and the simple pole $\lambda_0 = 0$, this solution is obtained by the formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
u(x, t) = & -2 \sum_{\substack{v=-\infty \\ v \neq 0}}^{\infty} \int_0^1 [((\xi - 1) \sin 2\pi v \xi \sin 2\pi v x - \\
& - x \cos 2\pi v x \cos 2\pi v \xi) \left(\frac{-1}{2\sqrt{v^4 - (2\pi v)^4 a^2}} [(\varphi_0(x) m_2 - \varphi_1(x)) e^{m_1 t} + \right. \\
& \left. + (\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_0(x) m_1) e^{m_2 t} + \int_0^t f(x, \tau) (e^{m_2(t-\tau)} e^{m_1(t-\tau)}) d\tau \right) - \\
& - \sin 2\pi v x \cos 2\pi v \xi \left(\frac{-(2\pi v)^3 a^2}{2(v^4 - (2\pi v)^4 a^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} [(\varphi_0(x) m_2 - \varphi_1(x)) e^{m_1 t} + \right. \\
& \left. + (\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_0(x) m_1) e^{m_2 t} + \int_0^t f(x, \tau) (e^{m_2(t-\tau)} - e^{m_1(t-\tau)}) d\tau \right) - \\
& - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{v^4 - (2\pi v)^4 a^2}} [\varphi_0(x) m_{2\lambda} e^{m_1 t} + t(\varphi_0(x) m_2 - \varphi_1(x)) m_{1\lambda} e^{m_1 t} - \varphi_0(x) m_{1\lambda} e^{m_2 t} + \\
& \left. + t(\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_0(x) m_1) m_{2\lambda} e^{m_2 t} + \int_0^1 f(x, \tau) (t - \tau) (m_{2\lambda} e^{m_2(t-\tau)} - m_{1\lambda} e^{m_1(t-\tau)}) d\tau \right)] d\xi
\end{aligned}$$

By imposing certain smoothness conditions on the functions $f(x, \tau)$, $\varphi_0(x)$ and $\varphi_1(x)$, it is proven that the obtained solution is classical.

References

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